

Midwest Bat Hub Hibernaculum Colony Count Database User Manual

Version 1.0
September 2024

[Contact Us](#)

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1. Introduction

In response to the challenges posed by varied winter colony count protocols across the Midwest, the Midwest Bat Hub has developed a Microsoft Access database to serve as a data management tool. The database is designed to facilitate standardization and consistency in winter colony count data. With data entry forms, it guides users in entering information consistently, reducing the risk of errors and facilitating a unified approach to data collection.

The database also features a premade query that allows users to filter records by a date range of interest and export the data in a format that fits the NABat hibernaculum colony count upload template. This is designed to facilitate partner integration with the NABat framework.

2. System Requirements

2.1 Installation Instructions

Before downloading the Hibernaculum Colony Count Database, please ensure that your system meets the following requirements:

Operating System: Microsoft Windows 7 or later

Processor: 2.0 GHz or faster.

RAM: 4 GB or higher.

Hard Disk Space: 10 GB of available space.

Microsoft Access: Version 2013 or later installed.

Note: If you encounter any issues during the installation process, please contact us for assistance.

3. General Overview of Access

3.1 Access Objects

Access databases consist of various object types. This particular database includes the following objects:

- **Tables:** Store and organize data in a structured format. They consist of rows and columns, where each row represents a record, and each column represents a field or attribute. Tables are the fundamental structures used for storing and managing data within the Access database system.
- **Queries:** Used to retrieve and manipulate data. They allow for precise data filtering, sorting, and calculations, facilitating efficient analysis and providing a foundation for form and report generation.
- **Forms:** Provide user-friendly interfaces for data entry, interaction, and presentation. They serve to input and edit data, enhancing the user experience in working with databases.

You will likely interact the most with forms for data entry and viewing purposes. To navigate through records in a form, here are some tips:

3.2 Record Navigation

- **First Record:** To navigate to the first record, click the 'First Record' button on the Navigation Bar.
- **Previous Record:** Move to the previous record by clicking the 'Previous Record' button.
- **Current Record:** The 'Current Record' box allows you to directly enter a record number and press Enter to jump to that specific record.
- **Next Record:** Move forward to the next record using the 'Next Record' button.
- **Last Record:** To quickly navigate to the last record, click the 'Last Record' button.
- **New Record:** Initiate a new, blank record for data entry by clicking the 'New Record' button.
- **Search Bar:** Utilize the search bar to quickly locate specific records. Enter keywords or criteria and press Enter to filter the displayed records.

3.2 Record Selector

- **Record Selector:** The Record Selector is the gray box located to the left of each record. Clicking on it selects the entire record.
- **Multi-Record Selection:** Hold down the Shift key while clicking on Record Selectors to select multiple records.
- **Record Deletion:** With the Record Selector, you can delete a selected record by clicking the 'Delete Record' button on your keyboard.
- **Batch Operations:** Perform batch operations on selected records, such as copying, cutting, or formatting.

4. MWBH Hibernaculum Colony Count Database Objects

4.1 Tables, Queries, and Forms

Tables

- **Site Table (tblSite):** Stores all unchanging site information.
- **Section Table (tblSection):** Stores unchanging information on the different sections within a larger site.
- **Visit Table (tblVisit):** Stores information on visits taken to each site.
- **Visit Section Table (tblVisitSection):** Stores environmental information collected at various sections during particular visits.
- **Bat Observation Table (tblBatObservation):** Stores information on observed bats.
- **Species Table (tblSpecies):** A list of all NABat-accepted species (serves as a lookup table).

Queries

- **NABat Colony Count Query (qryNABatColonyCount):** Used to retrieve information from the database and compile it in a format that allows for a direct upload to NABat.

Forms

- **Site Form (frmSite):** Used to view or enter information to the Site Table.
- **Section Form (frmSection):** Used view or to enter information to the Section Table.
- **Visit Form (frmVisit):** Used to view or enter information to the Visit Table, and the Section Table on the Visit datasheet (internal temperature and humidity of each section).
- **Bat Observation Form (frmBatObservation):** Used to view or enter information to the Bat Observation Table, and quickly filter and search through bat observation records, view reference photographs, and edit records if necessary.
- **Main Menu (frmMainMenu):** This form automatically loads when the database is opened. It allows for quick navigation through the database (tables and forms) and contains a button that generates an Excel file of the NABat Colony Count Query.

4.2 Lookup Fields

Some tables contain ‘Lookup Fields’— fields in a table that are connected to a set of values in another table or query. These fields can be useful in simple databases, as they allow users to select a value from a predefined list rather than entering data manually. Lookup fields also enhance user comprehension by displaying values instead of primary key numbers in tables (e.g., displaying “Site 1” in the Section Table to save a section to a site rather than displaying

the primary key corresponding to Site 1). However, it is important to know which fields are lookup fields, as though they might *display* text strings, they only *store* numeric values. This can affect the way you structure your queries. All lookup fields in this database are marked by a “_lkp” suffix at the end of the field name for quick identification.

5. Getting Started

5.1 Organizing Pictures

Before entering data into the database, it is recommended to organize reference bat photographs by visit into folders. In other words, all pictures taken at a particular site on a particular visit should be uploaded to one folder. This folder path will later be used to display images in the database.

The database currently only accepts JPEG images. If you wish to reference images in the database, please use a converter tool to ensure that all images are in this format.

Note: If not working on a shared drive, each time you send a database populated with data to another user, they will need to open the Visit Form, and replace the value in the “Path to Picture Folder” field with the updated folder path on *their* respective device.

5.2 Calculating GRTS ID Number Given Site Coordinates

If you do not wish to report sensitive latitude and longitude site information to NABat for privacy concerns, you can report the associated GRTS ID instead (these are 10x10km sample cells with randomly generated unique numeric identifiers). If you do not know the GRTS ID for your survey site, you can use the [NABat Grid Cell Finder](#) app hosted by Bat Conservation International and NABat. Here, you can enter latitude and longitude data and determine the corresponding GRTS ID for your sites.

5.3 Edit Trust Settings to Enable Content

Microsoft Access employs security features to protect users from potentially harmful content, especially when dealing with databases from untrusted sources. To ensure a smooth experience with your downloaded database, it might be necessary to adjust the Trust Center settings.

Accessing Trust Center Settings

1. Open the database.
2. Click on the ‘File’ tab in the top left of the Ribbon.
3. Select ‘Options’ at the bottom of the navigation pane. This will open the Access Options dialog.
4. In the dialog, click on ‘Trust Center’ in the left-hand navigation pane and click on the ‘Trust Center Settings...’ button on the right.
5. In the Trust Center, go to ‘Trusted Locations’, and click on ‘Add new location’.

6. Enter the folder path where your Access database is stored as a trusted location under the 'Path' field. This is typically the folder where the downloaded database file resides.
7. Click OK to save preferences.
8. Back in the Trust Center, go to 'Macro Settings'.
9. Choose the option 'Enable all macros (not recommended, potentially dangerous code can run)'.
10. Save preferences and close the database.
11. After making these changes, open your database back up again.
12. If prompted with a security warning bar at the top of the Access window, click on the 'Enable Content' button in the yellow bar to enable all content, including macros.

5.4 Backing up the Database

Regularly backing up your database is a critical practice to safeguarding data, allowing you to restore it in case of data loss, corruption, or other unforeseen issues. To back up your database:

1. Click on the "File" tab to access the Backstage view.
2. Choose "Save As" from the menu.
3. Save a copy of your database in a different location or use the "Save Database As" option to create a backup copy.
4. Select a secure location for your backup, such as an external drive, network location, or cloud storage.
5. Consider including the date in the backup file name for easy identification of when the backup was created.

6. Data Entry Guidelines

It is generally recommended that information in forms is entered in this order: Site, Section, Visit (including visit section information), and Bat Observation.

Site information should be entered first, as it will be later used in the Section Form, Visit Form, and Bat Observation Form. Similarly, bat observation data should be entered last, as it pulls information from the other forms (site, section, and visit forms).

6.1 General Guidelines

- Use forms, not tables, to enter data. Forms contain user friendly fields that automatically tie records back to parent tables, while tables lack the same clarity.
- Forms won't allow you to enter commas in any fields, since the final NABat report will have to be submitted in csv format. Any commas in the final NABat upload file will produce upload errors. Use semicolons instead of commas.
- When entering measurements that might be accompanied by units, enter only the number associated with the measurement and not the unit itself (e.g., if entering a wind speed that was 10 mph, type in "10" not "10 mph"). All such fields will be accompanied with a label showing the expected units of measurement. Convert units as needed before entering data.
- Fields highlighted in gray in forms cannot be edited, they are auto generated number fields (a unique, sequential number for each record that serves as a record identifier).
- While most forms come with an extensive number of fields, these can be left blank if the relevant data were not collected during the survey.

6.2 Record Navigation in Forms

- Each form includes search boxes located in the header section, allowing for quick navigation to specific records (see image below). These search boxes are unbound, meaning any values entered will not be saved to the underlying tables. Use them to easily search and locate records within the forms.

The image shows the header section of the 'BAT OBSERVATION FORM'. It features a dark green background with white text and input fields. On the left, the text 'BAT OBSERVATION FORM' is displayed. To the right, there are several search filters: 'Site', 'Section', 'Date', and 'Species', each with a dropdown arrow. Below these are 'Image Included' (with a radio button), 'Min Count', and 'Max Count', each with an input field. On the far right, there are 'Search' and 'Clear' buttons. A circular logo for the 'SOUTHWEST BAT HUB' is visible in the top right corner.

7. Editing the database

7.1 Deleting Records

Since Referential Integrity is enforced for relationships between tables, Access will not allow you to delete a parent record without first deleting all related child records. For instance, you will not be able to delete a record for a bat observation without first deleting all associated image records in 'tblBatImage'.

7.2 Other Edits

The database contains various related tables, forms, and queries. It is important to be aware of all dependent objects before making changes to an object (so that you are mindful of other objects that might be affected by this change). To view all dependencies of an object, you can use the 'Dependencies' feature in Access. To use this, click on the object of interest in the Navigation Pane. Then, under the 'Relationships' Group, click on 'Object Dependencies' to show all other objects that your object of interest depends on, as well as other objects that depend on it.

8. Troubleshooting

8.1 Issues with Opening or Loading Forms

If you are encountering any difficulty when trying to open a form (e.g., error messages are asking you to enter a parameter value, etc...), compiling the VBA code running in the background of the form is usually the resolution. To compile the background VBA code in any form:

- On the Ribbon, under the Create tab, navigate to the 'Macros & Code' Group.
- Click on 'Visual Basic' to open the visual basic editor window.
- On the top of the window that opens up, navigate to the 'Debug' tab.
- Click on 'Compile Database1'.

If any issues persist, please contact the Midwest Bat Hub.

8.2 Contact for Support

For any Database related questions, issues, or concerns, please contact the Midwest Bat Hub at nres-midwest-bathub@mx.uillinois.edu